

USING MODERN TEACHING METHODS IN ESL CLASSROOM

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Annotation: Modern teaching methods are the only way to meet the requirements of modern times. Modern teaching unquestionably is the need of the hour because of its relevance in the modern era. The revolution in the field of science and technology demands great ideas and extensive effort to deal with any kind of circumstances coming in the way of development, so it is vital to give students not only knowledge but to improve their skills from the beginning.

Key words: modern teaching methods, knowledge, skills, technology, interaction, learner-centred, task-based, resource-based, project-based, problem-based, peer-collaboration.

In recent years, the scope of knowledge in the field of science and technology has increased, and human's ability to adapt to new knowledge in science and technology has also increased. So, there is an immense need for innovative and creative minds to explore unknown and unrevealed areas of different fields. To cope up with the modern world and the knowledge-driven era of technology, adopting modern ways are the only means to survive.

So, the students should be taught in a manner to tackle the 21st century, which is technology-driven time and which requires creative and innovative minds for the progress of individuals, society, and nation. The students should be introduced with modern teaching techniques and are provided sufficient knowledge so that they can create opportunities for themselves and others.

The modern teaching method is more activity-based and centered the learner's mind which involves them entirely into the process of learning. In the modern teaching method, curriculum teaching and planning are done keeping the learner as the primary target. Through this way, learners actively participate in the whole process to build their knowledge and sharpen their skills.

On the other hand, the teacher only needs them and guides them to focus on the objectives of the subject. This is all done by engaging in activities and by adopting innovative modern teaching techniques.

Modern teaching methods are the only way to meet the requirements of modern times. Modern teaching unquestionably is the need of the hour because of its relevance in the modern era. The revolution in the field of science and technology demands great ideas and extensive effort to deal with any kind of circumstances coming in the way of development, so it is vital to give students not only knowledge but to improve their skills from the beginning. The modern teaching methods help to develop a productive understanding of basic science and technology. The elements of modern teaching methods include:

1. Learner-centred. One of essential characteristics of the modern teaching methods in basic science and technology is learner-centred. It focuses on learners while using or applying during classroom and lectures. In this method, the teacher acts only as a guide, and all the

learning process involves learners. Learners significantly appear as a dominator in classroom interactions.

2. Task-based (or activity-based). The teacher of basic science and technology organizes activity or task, and engages students to learn through this way. It is an activity-based or commission-based method. Students are offered or asked to take part in classroom interaction through these interactive activities.

3. Resource-based. For using this method of teaching, the teachers should collect and distribute all the required study material to the learners for their learning or to understand the topic clearly. The resources can be collected from any places where it is available. Also, a learner can be the source to bring study material or resources from their end.

4. Peer collaboration. Modern teaching methods not only encourage students by allowing them to present their ideas or initiative by noticing their responses, studying their research, and allowing them to answer during interaction in BST classes but also selects students based on interest, needs, and feelings. Through Instructional activities, students learn to work cooperatively, and they appreciate their competitors' work as well. In the BST curriculum, learner's interests are considered most important, and they are guided towards their goals and careers. There are different types of modern teaching methods:

1. Cooperative (or collaborative) learning. This type of modern teaching method is based on the concept of teamwork and collective efforts. It helps in developing social skills and allows students to understand the subject faster. In this modern teaching method, every student is a part of the success of a group as they help each other to reach the desired result, and they also learn to communicate with each other. Learners learn to tolerate others, develop skills to listen to others and how to work in a team. They will be able to meet different personalities and can get a genuine review of their work. Students present their ideas and expect a response when they are in group learning. It allows them to exchange their creativity and gain more knowledge. In return, it helps them to learn to face healthy criticism and cross-questions.

2. Project-Based Learning. The idea of project-based learning makes more sense in the 21st century education system. The projects refer to the tasks given to the students entirely associated with the field they are pursuing. They are provided with practical case studies which require the application of their skill set and knowledge to provide an optimum solution to the problem. These are challenged through the types of projects included in the project-based learning system.

3. Problem-Based Learning. The problem-based learning comprises a whole set of activities under the tag of problems and providing solutions which will enhance the skills and knowledge of the students to a greater extent. This will also provoke their enthusiasm level and initiates the problem-solving aspect of the thinking in their minds. According to the problem-based learning system, the teachers allow the students with a particular set of problems that will challenge their learnings and the acquired skills so far. The students need to solve the problem using their intelligence.

4. Spaced learning. Spaced learning is one of the modern teaching methods, which is being followed by teachers. In this method, teachers repeat a lesson multiple times, basically until the students understand entirely. However, the teacher repeats the course with two 10-minute spaces (break) in-between the lessons. This gap is meant to refresh the mind by playing activities or mindfulness techniques which prepares them for the next session of the

same lesson. This method gives the student intervals to inherit the knowledge and create connections between learnings.

5. Flipped classroom. Flipped classroom is a well known and vital modern teaching methods that has been in use these days. It has also proven to be productive and very efficient for the development of the students. According to the idea of the flipped classroom technique, the teachings methods are reversed as the word suggests.

In this method of teaching, students are asked to study new material themselves at home with necessary instructions (watching a video tutorial, search online, or work on the content) given by the teacher, and the classroom is converted into a centre of practical education. Through this method students get enough time to grasp the topic, they can also suggest their ideas related to the content and share it with other groupmates. If necessary, they can work more on one issue.

5. Self-learning. Curiosity pushes the learner to learn always new and more. It drives the learners to learn and memorize large spaces of the text that they will either miss gratefully or forget immediately. Through their curiosity, students get motivated to explore the subjects they are interested in. Teaching students to operate the internet and find results themselves helps them to be self-confident and gives them a deep understanding of the content.

A teacher should allow the students to bring new ideas and work on it for the development of their brain and ability to work alone. This modern teaching method plays a significant role in learners' period of education.

6. VAK teaching. VAK is a modern teaching method whose effects can be seen clearly. We divide learner into three categories: visual, audio and kinesthetic (movement). One needs to recognize to which category they belong to or the teacher must know to which category his/her students relate to. In VAK, V - is visual, means seeing the data, A - is audio, means gathering information by hearing the data, and K - is kinesthetic, means feeling the data. A teacher should keep the category of students in kind while teaching because some students catch the information by seeing, by hearing, or by feeling. So, they should present the same material in different ways.

The VAK teaching method was introduced in the 1920s to help children with dyslexia. However, its impact is more effective in the modern era. In the time of the Internet, watching and learning through videos has become a popular new medium of teaching. Students grasp fast when they see, hear, or feel instead of reading the material. And also, a learner is not limited to any one of the media as they can use even all three mediums of instruction.

In conclusion, there are some advantages of modern teaching methods:

1. Modern teaching methods are interactive and keep students intact. In this method of teaching, the teacher asks the students to form small groups or work as individuals to perform the learning tasks and come up with the desired results. It helps students to gather knowledge from one another. Students learn to work together and a sense of cooperation.
2. Modern teaching methods are integrative. Teachers link topics of one subject, e.g., social science topics like drug use, domestic violence, safety, pollution, food distribution, crime etc. to other issues and make it integrative. By this, a learner can gain knowledge of more topics studying one.
3. The visual medium is better than any other medium to give instructions. It helps to memorize the concept fast and for a more extended period than reading;

4. Modern teaching methods are less time-consuming. Teachers take less time to cover the syllabus. Writing on the blackboard is not required;
5. Blackboard explanation of content is less explanatory than a representation of videos and animations used in the modern teaching techniques.

Advantages of modern teaching methods should consider conventional methods of teaching as its base and learners should not neglect it completely while incorporating the new ones. However, modern teaching methods are suitable for the current century to cope up with surroundings and environments. Also, it is the responsibility of teachers to teach students with suitable and modern methods.

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